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The Joint Ambition of Nepal & Diplomacy with the Maratha Empire (1815-1818).

The Gorkha Kingdom, later renamed the Kingdom of Nepal, under the leadership of Prithvi Narayan Shah (1743-1775), succeeded in unifying the fragmented Himalayan kingdoms during the 18th century, especially after the conquest of the Kathmandu Valley between 1768 and 1769. After the death of Prithvi Narayan Shah, his successors continued his policy of further territorial acquisition in the western regions. The Gorkhalis captured the territories of Kumaon around 1790-1791 and Garhwal between 1803 and 1804. Their territorial gains took them into the foothills of the Himalayas, where they briefly reached the Kangra region (now Himachal Pradesh) around 1806-1809 under the command of Amar Singh Thapa. They clashed with the forces of Maharaja Ranjit Singh's Sikh Empire around 1809. Although the Gorkhalis were successful, the Sikhs emerged victorious, forcing the Gorkhalis to withdraw to the eastern side of the Sutlej River. The Gorkha Empire was at its peak during the early nineteenth century and was a powerful empire, controlling a vast part of the Himalayas, stretching from the Tista River to the regions near the Sutlej River. However, the Gorkha Empire's territorial gains were halted by its defeat in the Anglo-Nepalese War (1814-1816), after which the Treaty of Sugauli forced Nepal to cede the

territories of Kumaon, Garhwal, and other regions of the western part of Nepal to the British.

नयाँ नेपाली

मान्छेलाई ठिक्क मात्रै कमाउन दिनु। किन भनौला, दौलत भएकोले तरबार मा पसि मर्न मर्न सक्दैनन्, र हरिप (शत्रु) को फेला पर्छन्। सिपाही, भै-भारदार ले सोख गरे भने चारै दिशाबाट मा मेरो तरबार बज्ने छ। मेरा साना दुख ले आर्जेको मुलुक होइन, सबै जात को फुलवारि हो। सबै लाई चेतना होस्। यो फुलवारि हो छोटो बडा चारै जात छत्तीसै वर्ण को। यो असली हिन्दुस्थान हो। आफ्ना कुलधर्म न छोड्नु।

English translation

Let them earn money according to their ability. You may ask, "Why do so?" That is because the extra wealth breeds laziness and they cannot use their sword and there will be supremacy of enemies. If the soldiers, royalties and public officials become addicted to pleasure, my sword will follow them from all four directions.

This nation is not built by small toil. This is a garden of all the castes, everybody should acknowledge it. It is a garden of all the four castes and thirty-six creeds. This is the real Hindusthan (place of Hindus). Do not give up your religion (Kul-dharma).

- Divya Upadesh Prithvi Narayan Shah, PDF Page No. (28/47)

[Prithvi Narayan Shah's Divya Upadesh \(Translated into English\)](#)

Prithvi Narayan Shah quoted Nepal as "Real Hindustan". Meaning the Real Land of Hindus during the Period of Islamic Rule in India. India compared to Nepal, was no longer considered the Land of Hindus. Additionally, quoting Nepal as the Garden of Four Castes and Thirty-Six Creeds. Shivaji also had the Same Ambition for the self-determination of Hindus. Famous

for his Ambition of Hindavi Swarajya. There is no doubt that Prithvi Narayan Shah was a Zealous Ruler likewise Shivaji.

The first and foremost ideal put by the elders before the young Shivarai was the protection of his religion from the onslaughts of the Muslims who were styled Mlechhas. For instance, his preceptor Kond Deva impressed upon his receptive mind that ‘the whole earth is trampled down by the foreigners. All places, forts and towns are full of their forces. Important places should be possessed by you. Hindu kings and Hindu forces should be secured by you for your assistance. You should perform difficult deeds by supreme industry and daring. Then you will obtain the blessings of saints and the approval of God for your success.’¹

- Shivaji the Great by Bal Krishna PDF Page No. (187/243)

[Shivaji the Great - Bal Krishna PDF](#)

Shivaji also had the same ambition for the self-determination of Hindus. He dedicated most of his Life to the Ideal of Hindavi Swarajya to the Mughal Muslims. The Deccan, to which Shivaji was exposed, believed that his whole World was haunted by the Mughals. Shivaji conquered multiple forts during his Lifetime. Being Considered as one of the Greatest Generals in Indian History and the Greatest General in 16th Century India. He also conquered the Principality of Thanjavur (Tanjore) in Tamil Nadu to which his Half Brother Vyankoji was given to Rule. It is also important to note that Lord Shiva was a Primary Deity for both Shivaji and Prithvi Narayan Shah.

Prithvi Narayan Shah Glorified the Nepalese Empire under his Domain. His famous quote that Nepal is a Yam between two Stones, mentioned below.

नयाँ नेपाली

॥ उप्रान्त ॥ यो राज्य दुई ढुङ्गा को तरुल जस्तो रहे छ। चीनको बादशाह सित ठूलो घाहा राख्नु। दक्षिण को समुन्द्र का बादशाह (अङ्ग्रेज) सित घाहा ता राख्नु, तर त्यो महा-चतुर छ। हिन्दुस्थान दबाई राखेको छ। सरजिमी मा परि रहे छ। हिन्दुस्थान (राजा र प्रजा) जम्यो भने (मिल्यो भने) कठिन पर्ला भनि किल्ला खोज्न आउने छ। सन्धि सर्पन् हेरि गढि तुल्याई राख्नु र रस्ता-रस्ता मा भाँजा हालि राख्नु र एक दिन त्यो बल आउने छ। जाइ कटक (लडाई) नगर्नु, झिकी कटक गर्नु। र चुरे घाटी मा खुब काट्न सकिन्छ, पाँच सात पुस्ता लाई खजाना पनि मिलने छ। श्री गङ्गाजी सम्म सिमाना पनि पुग्नेछ।

English translation

This state (Nepal) is like a yam between two stones. Keep a strong friendship with the emperor of China. Maintain friendship with the emperor of the sea (English emperor) in the south, but he is very clever. He has suppressed Hindustan (India). He is eyeing the plane area (of Nepal). If Hindustani (Indian king and people) unite, they (the English) may find it difficult to stay there and search for a safe fort (towards Nepal). Maintain the treaty, find out weak points and build strong forts. Create obstacles in the way. They will surely arrive here one day. Do not attack them, but if they attack, fight with them. They can be beheaded at the crossings of the Chure hills, and we will be able to collect treasures (arms and ammunition) sufficient for our five to seven generations. And the border can be extended up to the Ganga River.

- Divya Upadesh Prithvi Narayan Shah, PDF Page No. (22/47)

[Prithvi Narayan Shah's Divya Upadesh \(Translated into English\)](#)

It is, in fact, obvious that it was a Dream of every Hindu power's wish for Conquest till the Ganga River, among only those who wished for glory. Chhatrapati Shivaji, the Founder of the Maratha Empire, also wanted the Marathas to expand till the Ganges and Delhi. Peshwa Baji Rao I of the Maratha Empire fulfilled this. The Son of Balaji Vishwanath. After this, the Peshwa Post became Hereditary due to the Legacy of Baji Rao from the Dynasty of the Chitpavan Bhattas; the Peshwas were irreplaceable. They were now the Dominant Power in India, with Emperor Shahu as Chhatrapati, the Grandson of Shivaji. The Expansion of the Ganges was likely a wish because the territory along the Ganges was never peaceful. And a Hindu Power would've had the Privilege of a Prestigious Proclamation of Calling themselves the Protectors of the Ganges due to it being in the Midst of Central India, where both Nepal and the Deccan were far which would also give them the Benefit of being "Long Conquerors", The Territory of Ganges is also a Region of Pilgrimage Central to the Hindu Faith.

13. The last will and testament of Shivaji is significant in showing his ideals and ambitious programmes. He exhorted his officers to put forth all their energy for the extension of the Maratha kingdom to the furthermost confines of India and for capturing the throne of Delhi; to free the sacred Ganges from the yoke of the Muslims; to cross the Indus and implant the Maratha flag in the trans-Indus Himalayas. “ It was my intense desire to conquer the whole of India, but I have not fulfilled it on account of my premature death. You should all attempt to realize this high ideal. The kingdom founded by me should be consolidated and extended with more heroism than I have ever exhibited.”

1. Shivaji, Part III, 282.

- Shivaji the Great by Bal Krishna PDF Page No. (47/243)

[Shivaji the Great - Bal Krishna PDF](#)

The First Instance of Contact we have with the Nepalese Empire after the Death of Prithvi Narayan Shah during the Period of the Marathas was in 1815, when an Instruction was sent to Amar Simha Thapa by Bhimsen Thapa on how to deal with the Neighbours of Gorkhas during their Expansions in India. His instruction was to engage in Diplomacy with the Nawab of Oudh, the Sikhs, and the Marathas. Along with the Rulers of Garhwal in Speciality due to the close Borders and Skirmishes.

The second set of regulations deals with foreign relations and the internal political affairs of the vassal state of Garhwal. The main points are summarized below:

Remain prepared to resist external aggression, if any, but do not engage in any aggression from our side. If the enemy invades our territory, defend our headquarters, and strike at him where he is weakest. If your forces prove insufficient, recruit additional troops.

Engage in regular correspondence with the English, the Nawab (of Oudh), and the Sikhs, the Marathas, and other powers in the western region. In consultation with the ruler of Garhwal, engage in similar correspondence with the rulers of the western principalities, including Sirmur and Kangra. Ascertain how many rulers side with Kangra, how many are opposed to it, and how many will support us if we proceed westward.

- 1999 Imperial Accounts of Gorkhali Rule in Kumaon 1791-1815. PDF Page No (74/174) [Imperial Accounts of Gorkhali Rule in Kumaon 1791-1815 PDF](#)

It might also be true that the Ambition of the Gorkhas was not only Money & Power, like most of the Hindu kings. Very few Hindu kings are quoted in History where they fought in Wars primarily for “Religion”. The Gorkhas, likely too, were Zealous. In the Midst of 1816, during the Expansion of the EIC, the Gorkhas wanted a Tripartite Alliance with the Maratha Empire and the Sikhs due to their collective hatred of the Expansion of the British. The Gorkhas also wrote, “that God will grant victory to the Hindus”. It was most likely that the Sikhs were included since they were drawn to Hinduism

compared to Islam or any Foreign Religion after centuries of Conquest and were an emerging power in Punjab.

Once the cavalry of the Sikhs and the Marahatta, and the infantry and muskets and cannon of the Gorkhalis, are joined together, God will make Hindus victorious in this war.

- 1999 Imperial Accounts of Gorkhali Rule in Kumaon 1791-1815. PDF Page No (32/174) [Imperial Accounts of Gorkhali Rule in Kumaon 1791-1815 PDF](#)

The Prime Minister of Nepal, Bhimsen Thapa, had sent his Emissary to Daulat Rao Scindia, the then Subahdar of Gwalior, after the death of Mahadji Scindia in 1794. North India was complicated to handle. The adoptive father of Daulat Rao Scindia, Mahadji Scindia, had already beaten the British in the 1st Anglo-Maratha War and was a Resurrector of Marathas after the Disastrous Defeat of Panipat against the Durrani Afghans in 1761. The British were also an upcoming threat. During this period, the Maratha Unity was also challenged with the Holkars fighting the Scindias. It was the Holkars and both the Scindias who ruled Northern India, with Holkar ruling Parts of Rajputana and Southern Malwa centered in Indore and Scindia spearheading the North, centered in Gwalior, clashing with the Sikhs in the Region of Punjab before the Unification of Punjab by Ranjit Singh and controlling the Mughal Emperor in Delhi.

Thus, during the third Anglo-Mahratta war which followed in the immediate wake of the Nepal war, the Nepalese tried to form a confederacy of the Mahrattas and the Pindaris against the British. A tried emissary, Pandit Padmapanee, was sent to Daulat Rao Sindhia for this purpose. Padmapanee sent from Gwalior a detailed report to Kathmandu referring to the Mahratta politics, and the attitude of the Peshwa, Holkar and Sindhi towards the British. On being asked by Sindhi about Nepal's reactions to the imminent war, (Anglo-Mahratta war), Padmapanee said :

The Maharaja [Sindhia] was the prince of the Deccan ; that if he would enter into serious and solemn engagements with my master and ratify them with religious ceremonies ...that in every way we should be ready and should act according to writing ; that we did not fear the English ; that we should enter into no agreement with them ; that if we made one, nothing after could be done, on which the Maharaja Sindhia gave me every assurance of satisfaction... The Poona affairs are thus : Trimbakji Danglia has created great tumult...and the English had opposed the Peshwa who has now yielded up some of his best forts...his army is opposed to them. If you get ready, I am willing to engage them... There is no dependence on their words... The Pindaries amount to 25000, and have brought spoil by the plunder of the European country who have killed many of their sowars. Notwithstanding, the Pindaries are still very strong and ready to fight, but they have no place of strength... Their safety is from Daulat Rao. The Europeans are ready to oppose them... The Maharaja's ministers have leagued with the English, this alarms and prevents him from quarrelling with them... The Maharaja [Sindhia] and

Hindu Rao wish to send you [King of Nepal] letters, but defer it on account of the road. I shall bring them with me¹⁰.

No restrictive or punitive measures were taken against Nepal, nor were her agents in Mahratta courts arrested or detained. A mild remonstrance alone was made with the Nepalese *darbar*. Soon after, the British entered into treaties with Sindhia and Amir Khan, the knowledge of which damped the zeal of the Nepalese *darbar* to forge offensive leagues with them. Following the Resident's representation, the *darbar* officially disavowed the activities of Padmapanee¹⁴.

- Anglo-Nepalese Relations in the Nineteenth Century by Kanchanmoy Mojumdar, PDF Page No. (35-36/214) [Anglo-Nepalese Relations in the Nineteenth Century PDF](#)

The British then entered Treaties as some British officers thought the Nepalese were “toying” for Dominance. They, regardless, still ended up entering Treaties with the Gorkhas & Marathas and the Sikhs altogether as a Tripartite to stall the Alliance Temporarily.

The British at first did not take these developments seriously. The Resident, Edward Gardner, even asserted that Nepal was just toying with a hope and that she had no malicious intention. Shortly, however, he was “pretty certain” that the Nepalese really meant mischief¹².

- Anglo-Nepalese Relations in the Nineteenth Century by Kanchanmoy Mojumdar, PDF Page No. (36/214) [Anglo-Nepalese Relations in the Nineteenth Century PDF](#)

Daulat Rao Scindia also considered if the Nepalese had a Plot in alliance with the British regarding the Plans of the Nepalese for a Tripartite however, Daulat Rao Scindia then stated that the Responsibility of keeping the Peshwa was now only in the Hands of the Gorkhas as a Power. The Marathas could've only trusted Nepalese because the Sikhs had previously fought the

Marathas in a series of Battles and Skirmishes due to their Encroachments of Doab, Panipat & Delhi in the period of the 1790s.

Sindhia's immediate reaction was one of doubt as regards Nepal's sincerity; he, therefore, refused to commit himself to Nepalese plans, wondering if they were not a British stratagem to know his attitude to the war. Very soon, however, Sindhia gave up his hesitancy and actively tried to forge a league of the Marhattas, the Sikhs and the Nepalese. The Peshwa, in the meanwhile, earnestly sought Gurkha military assistance, for he felt that "if there is anyone to save the Peshwa and now, that is to be done by the Gurkhas to whom everybody here look." Military preparations were set afoot in Nepal, evidently to keep the army in readiness for this anticipated league. The *darbar* urged the British to abrogate the Treaty of Sagouli, which the Nepalese resented as a national disgrace, and to substitute it by a new treaty, omitting altogether the article providing for the cession of the lowlands between the rivers Kosi and Gandak to the British¹¹.

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The British signed Treaties with Amir Khan, the Pindari Leader of Marathas and the Nepalese due to their Collective Interests of forging an Anti-British Tripartite and it being successful. However, it did not prove well as the British annexed all Maratha Territory in 1818, effectively ending the Maratha Empire and establishing the Subahdars of the Marathas as Equal “Maharajahs” of India, where they were centered. The Scindias in Gwalior and the Holkars in Indore, the Gaekwads had autonomy with the British and were in Power in Baroda, and weren't anti-British, who also aided the British in the 2nd Anglo-Maratha War against Central Maratha Powers.

Raghunathrao and his Descendants were also Problematic as they lost Power in an attempt to Regain Power during the Anglo-Maratha Wars among the Marathas slowly. The Reputation of Raghunathrao was already in Ruin after his involvement with the Tragic Murder of Narayanrao. However, in the wake of the 3rd Anglo-Maratha War, the Peshwas aligned with the Interests of the Holkars and Scindias, and so did the Bhonsales of Nagpur and the Pindari Leaders. Almost the Entire Maratha Empire fought this time, except for the Gaekwad of Baroda, and were then defeated, with Multiple Treaties signed. All the Maratha Princely States except for the Peshwas, who lost their Autonomy Completely as the post “Peshwa” are now nowhere to be seen, let alone in Power. The Maharajahs, who were previously Subahdars, were kept under British watch and under their Administration Policies, and with the Doctrine of Lapse proving effective, they removed a lot of Maratha Monarchs, such as the Rani of Jhansi, Rani Lakshmibai, in the Rebellion of 1858. And the Bhonsale Descendant of Tanjore in 1855. and with Baji Rao's adopted son Nanasahab II in Cawnpore in the same year as 1858, who rebelled against the British, who would be seen as the Successor of the

Peshwa Lineage. And also the Nawab of Banda from the Lineage of Baji Rao and Mastani, the Scindias in Gwalior also rebelled in the Period of 1843 in the Gwalior Rebellion before the Indian Rebellion of 1858, with some factions in 1858. The Peshwas are nowhere to be heard today after 1858, effectively. The Holkars on the other hand, supported the British in the Rebellion of 1858, which shows the Divided Politics of the Marathas in the Rebellion of 1858. The Gorkhas were also kicked out of British India with the Treaty of Sagauli in 1816. And now they were centered in Nepal, Gorkhas then protected Nepal from an offensive British Influence by allying themselves to the British, Nepal had to prove its allegiance to the British by helping the British suppress the Indian Rebellion of 1858 to where the Marathas were a primary key of power against the British along with the Mughals and other Sultanates centered in the Subcontinent the Sultanates who in fact were rivals were now short term allies rebelling against the British with whom the Marathas fought Awadh in Panipat and Rohillakhand who previously fought the Marathas separately after Panipat and in Panipat were now collectively allied fighting the British. The Rebellion of 1858 was the Last Intersection between the Marathas and the Gorkha Kingdom of Nepal.